

2025 Annual General Meeting - Thailand

Conference Proceedings

July 20 - 25, 2025

Contributors

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Special thanks to the conference participants whose discussions inspired and informed this report

Background of the Annual General Meeting

Climate change is driving the spread of climate-sensitive infectious diseases (CSIDs), creating urgent challenges for public health. Digital tools like climate-informed early warning systems have the potential to predict and prevent outbreaks, but efforts are often fragmented and disconnected from the communities most affected ([Ryan et al. 2023](#)). The CSID Network, established in 2024 through a [participatory design process](#), seeks to change this by connecting experts across disciplines and geographies fostering collaboration to develop tools that are both impactful and grounded in real-world needs.

2025 marks a milestone for the CSIDNet community of practice: our first-ever Annual General Meeting (AGM)! Interest to come together and foster this community of practice was so high that we decided to hold two gatherings simultaneously - one in-person and one virtual. After an open call for co-hosts through which the team at Mahidol Oxford Tropical Medicine Research Unit (MORU) at Mahidol University was selected, planning for the conference began in earnest in December 2024. The planning committee laid out a vision for a gathering that aimed to:

- Strengthen relationships within the network by fostering deeper connections among fellows, committees, and members, ensuring people know who to reach out to for support and collaboration.
- Collaboratively generate and refine new working group proposals while building shared skills and capacities for inclusive decision-making.
- Grow committee membership to sustain network activities.

Date and Venue

The 2025 CSIDNet Annual General Meeting was held from July 21 to 25, 2025 in Thailand. The gathering was facilitated by Cheekay Cinco with additional facilitation support by Amethyst Carey and Angela Okune. The complete program is provided in Appendix 1.

Participants

The AGM was attended by 65 participants from 35 countries. 49 participants were able to attend thanks to support from the CSIDNet "Inclusive Participation Fund" which offered stipends to alleviate the financial barriers of participation such as the cost of airfare, accommodations, and meals.

The gathering made clear that there continues to be a strong appetite for working even more closely across disciplines, geographies, and areas of expertise to advance climate-sensitive infectious disease research and tools. In what follows, we attempt to re-create the energy and summarize some of the conversations from our time together in Thailand.

Committee Pre-Conference Meeting - Sunday, 20 July

Building Together: Reflections on Committee Service

Our week began on Sunday with the All-Hands Committee Meeting, a preamble to the full program ahead. Over lunch, Committee members reconnected, and for many, it was the first time meeting in person after months of online collaboration. Having traveled long distances to be part of this gathering, members welcomed the chance to share a meal, exchange ideas, and begin building stronger relationships.

The afternoon opened with reflections on why members chose to serve, what they hope to contribute, and challenges they had encountered so far, facilitated by Amethyst Carey, CSIDNet's Governance Coach.

Many spoke about wanting to stay connected to the network, learn more about what Fellows and peers are building, and lend their skills to a young but growing community. For some, Committee work has been a way to meet new colleagues, exchange learnings, and develop new skills. For others, it has been more of a surprise, an ongoing discovery process requiring patience, trust, and a willingness to learn together. Committees emphasized the importance of balancing synchronous and asynchronous work, so that everyone can make the most of limited meeting time. Above all, they agreed that while volunteer service can be demanding, it should remain meaningful and rewarding, supported by a culture of collaboration.

The day closed with a co-working session focused on setting priorities for the months ahead.

Day 1 - Monday, 21 July

“What can we do together that we can't do alone?”

Monday marked the first full day of the gathering, when all 65 participants from 35 countries came together. The welcoming remarks set a powerful tone, reminding us that CSIDNet is designed to be a member-led community. From the start, we were invited to think beyond the tools and models, and to focus on what makes this network unique: our connections across differences.

"Political leaders throughout history have often used difference as a tactic of division, to fuel fear, hate, and prevent solidarity. But we strive to embrace our many differences as a source of strength. It is through respect, trust, care, and mutual learning that we can build a foundation for transformative science and collaboration.

What can we do together that we cannot do alone? I invite you to challenge yourself. Push to make a spark - a connection - a moment. That is our task this week."

- Angela Okune, CSIDNet Interim Managing Director

The conference lead facilitator, Cheekay Cinco, invited us to pause and acknowledge the privilege of being able to gather in these times, reminding us that such privilege should not paralyze us, but rather call us to action, to use this opportunity as momentum for the work ahead. The participants were invited to write down on pieces of paper what they were bringing to the gathering, both fears / anxieties and hopes, and store them in a collective bag. These were never meant to be read out loud but rather to help reflect and ground us in this moment. Then, we had an open conversation to collectively build our community agreements for the gathering.

(Click [HERE](#) to view the compilation of flipcharts curated by the committees)

While CSIDNet is a global, remote-first network, we believe it is essential to have strong, place-based roots in the locations where we gather. For this reason, we strive to co-host our AGMs with local organizations that are advancing relevant CSID work. In 2025, we were honored to partner with the Mahidol Oxford Tropical Medicine Research Unit (MORU) at Mahidol University's Faculty of Tropical Medicine in Bangkok, Thailand. CSIDNet members Professors Wirichada

Pan-Ngum and Kristen Aiemjoy played a central role, providing leadership throughout the eight months of planning. Thanks to their guidance and their team's incredible support, the event truly shone.

After opening remarks by the co-hosts and Wellcome Trust, our funding partner, the first day unfolded with a rich mix of parallel thematic discussions (find details in Appendix 2), flash talks showcasing early warning systems, and an interactive "Ask a Climate Expert" session, giving all participants the chance to share knowledge, best practices, and spark new ideas.

The "Ask a Climate Expert" session at the Thailand AGM in particular created space for participants to engage directly with a climate scientist on the use of climate data in CSID research, modeling, and prediction. Key insights included the importance of being precise with definitions, since common terms like "variability," "change," and "mitigation" are often used differently by different people. Participants were cautioned not to blindly trust gridded data or to assume that smaller-scale datasets are inherently better: for example, mosquitoes do not experience the temperature of a road surface, so researchers must ensure the data truly reflects relevant environmental conditions. We learned that historical climate data is more reliable, while future predictions are inherently more uncertain, making it critical to involve climate scientists early in research design.

After such a full program, we enjoyed a special dinner cruise along the Chao Phraya River. With food, music, dancing, and the illuminated temples of Bangkok passing by, the night was filled with joy and connection. Even navigating public transit together became part of the adventure. It was a reminder that, beyond the work we do, community building is also about the moments we share.

Day 2 - Tuesday, 22 July

We kicked off the second day with a visit to Mahidol University, the conference co-host, for a behind-the-scenes look at what it means to do public health research on the ground in Thailand. From a state-of-the-art surveillance center to a hands-on lab practice, the tour offered the chance to see the science in context, and gave us a peek at how research connects with policy, education, and daily life.

Center of Excellence for Biomedical and Public Health Informatics (BIOPHICS)
<https://www.biophics.org>

At the Center of Excellence for Biomedical and Public Health Informatics, the Director, Mr. Amnat Khamsiriwatchara traced how decades of work have transformed malaria surveillance in Thailand. What began as paper-based records has evolved into a state-of-the-art system with streamlined data intake and harmonization pipelines, visualized through a user-friendly dashboard. This

progress has required not only technical innovation, but also extensive coordination across government agencies to establish data standards and enforce rapid case reporting. The lecture offered a valuable lesson on how disease surveillance and outbreak response depends as much on collaboration and governance as on technical expertise.

Discovery Museum of Tropical Diseases

At the Discovery Museum of Tropical Diseases, we stepped into an immersive exhibition through the history and impact of Mahidol University's Faculty of Tropical Medicine. The Museum highlights the Faculty's major contributions to research that have shaped our understanding of tropical diseases and their impact on society. We were guided through the life cycles of vectors and pathogens, from widely known diseases like malaria to those that receive less attention, such as the liver fluke. The exhibitions demonstrated how public education and outreach can turn research into accessible and engaging knowledge beyond the lab.

Lab of the Department of Medical Entomology

What does it take to run a research program on vector control and insecticide resistance? It turns out, you need live mosquitos, lots of them. At the Department of Medical Entomology, we got a close up look at how researchers breed and maintain mosquito colonies by replicating environmental conditions for each stage of their lifecycle, and then had the chance to try it ourselves through hands-on practice. The visit was a vivid reminder that, alongside computational models and tools, lab work grounds our understanding of disease transmission.

After lunch, we headed west to Kanchanaburi, the town where we would spend the rest of the week. The drive took us out of the city, through rice fields, and into a lush landscape where the mountains meet the river, and where our conversations would shift to thinking together what comes next for the network.

Day 3 - Wednesday, 23 July

Building stronger roots

With the move to Kanchanabui, our focus shifted inward, toward the Committees and Working Groups that hold the network together. The day began with Committee Updates in the style of a fast-paced World Café. In three minutes, Committees shared an overview of their ongoing work, which is laying the foundations for CSIDNet. Long coffee breaks in between provided space for informal conversations and picking up threads from earlier discussions.

In the afternoon, we turned our attention to brainstorming Working Groups proposals. Ideas poured in from across the community. Similar themes emerged, from model repositories to ethical data use frameworks, and gradually diverse ideas began to cluster together. These groups became the basis for parallel discussions, where members worked to flesh out proposals.

The evening offered unstructured time for self-organized activities. Members organized visits to Kanchanaburi's night market, and the railway bridge over the Khwae Yai River. The sense of community and connection carried through every part of the day, from structured sessions to the spaces in between.

Day 4 - Thursday, 24 July

Democratic Governance in Practice

On Thursday, we dived deeper into the policies and frameworks that guide and sustain our network. Committees led parallel discussions, inviting input on key issues and giving members the space to move between conversations. Our community brought different priorities and perspectives into dialogue, searching for common ground with thoughtfulness and generosity. Some members even stepped forward to serve in Committees to help shape these evolving decisions. This is what democratic governance and shared leadership look like in practice: hard work, respectful dialogue and collective decision-making across differences. To capture the breadth of discussions, Committees created posters summarizing their work, which were displayed in a Gallery Walk. The day closed with a joint session *"What Comes Next? From Recommendation to Reality"*, linking in-person and virtual participants that had been having a parallel AGM online.

Seeing the foundations of the network take shape has been exciting; the day showed how much progress has been made, and important work still to come.

Parallel Committee Sessions

- Membership and Partnerships Committee: *Affirming our Network Membership Structure*
- Research and Comms Committee: *CSID Network Comms Strategy*
- Governance Committee: *Committee Term Limits and (S)election process*
- Ad Hoc Working Group Committee: *Clarifying the Working Group Selection and Funding Process*
- Governance Committee: *Reporting & Information Sharing Practices*
- Fellows: *Building Local Communities of Practice*
- Membership and Partnerships Committee: *Affirming our Onboarding and Outreach Activities*
- Fundraising & Finance Committee: *Inclusive Participation Fund*
- *Emergent Network Sessions*

Day 5 - Friday, 25 July

Looking ahead

The last day of the gathering opened leisurely, a gentle start after an intense week of work and connection. We closed out with the CSIDNet signature clap circle, a tradition that began in 2023 during our first in-person gathering. Each person shared five words that captured their experience. Words like “Community” and “Connection” came up repeatedly, emphasizing the values that carried us throughout the week, and leaving us with gratitude, solidarity, and a shared sense of purpose for the work ahead.

As we wrapped up the week, we left feeling inspired and energized about what comes next. The Working Groups emerging from these conversations will serve as a launching point for this collaborative science to grow and take root. With so much momentum and shared purpose, we are excited to see how these efforts will translate into action in the months ahead.

Appendix 1: 2025 AGM Program - Thailand

<p>Day 0 (20 July / Sunday)</p> <p>International participants arriving at Eastin Hotel Phayathai</p> <p>Committees' All-Hands Meeting (lunch start at noon @ Mo Chit Room, 6th floor, Eastin Hotel) Committee Meeting from 1 PM - 4 PM</p>	
<p>Day 1 (21 July / Monday)</p> <p>Location: Siam Hall 6th Floor, Eastin Hotel</p>	
Time	Activity
08:30 - 09:00	Registration and ice breaker activity
09:00 - 10:15	<p>Opening the gathering</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Welcoming remarks ● Community agreements ● Agenda setting
10:15 - 10:30	Coffee break
10:30 - 12:00	<p>Parallel Sessions (1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Advances in Multi-Scale and Predictive Modeling for Climate-Sensitive Disease Forecasting – Leonardo Rafael Lopez, Sisay Adall ● Citizen Science and Participatory Approaches – Karen Cheruto Bett ● Principles and Ethics of Generative AI in CSID Tools - Shakira Babirye ● Antimicrobial Resistance and Environmental Drivers – Muhammad Asaduzzaman ● Storms, Natural Disasters, and Infectious Diseases - Kelly Searle
12:00 - 13:00	Lunch break
13:00 - 13:30	Group photo
13:30 - 15:00	Parallel Sessions (2)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vector-Borne Infectious Diseases and the Role of Climate Change – Ibrahima Diouf, Daniel Villela, Jared Norman • Feasibility and Appropriateness of Ensemble Models in LMICs – Angkana Huang • Co-Designing a Simulation Game for CSID - Sebastian Bernal-Garcia • Risk Communication for Climate-Sensitive Infectious Diseases - Sharon Tshipa • Open Science, R Packages, and Research Software Development – Yanina Bellini Saibene, Samuel Schildhauer
15:00 - 15:15	Coffee break
15:15 - 16:15	Flash Talks: Showcase of Early Warning Systems and Tools
16:15 - 17:00	<p>“Ask a Climate Expert a Question”</p> <p>This session is an opportunity to learn from the experiences of the climate experts in the room by asking them questions about trends, ways of utilising climate data for research, and anything else you might want to ask them.</p> <p>Note: We will be asking participants to write down their questions at the beginning of and throughout the 1st day.</p>
17:00 – 17:15	Closing the day
18:00	Check-in at the Alangka Cruise Counter at Pier 4
19:15	Cruise departs from the ICONSIAM Pier
21:15	Cruise returns to ICONSIAM Pier
<p>Day 2 (22 July / Tuesday)</p> <p>Location: Department of Tropical Hygiene, Mahidol University</p>	
08:00	Check-out from Eastin
08:30	Meet in lobby; take vans to Mahidol University
09:00 - 10:30	<p>Open the day</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mahidol University Tour <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Center of Excellence for for Biomedical and Public Health Informatics (BIOPHICS) ○ Discovery Museum of Tropical Diseases

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Lab of the Department of Medical Entomology
10:40 - 11:00	Coffee break in the meeting room 9th Tranakchit Harinasuta Building
11:10 - 11:50	Mahidol University Tour, continued
12:00 - 13:00	Lunch in the meeting room 9th Tranakchit Harinasuta Building
13:30 - 16:00	Travel to Kanchanaburi. The trip will take approximately 2.5 hours.
18:30	Pre-Arranged Buffet Dinner at Dheva Mantra Hotel
<p>Day 3 (23 July / Wednesday) Location: Monthathip @ Dheva Mantra Hotel in Kanchanaburi</p>	
09:00 - 10:00	Opening the Kanchanaburi Gathering
10:00 - 11:00	Committee Updates
11:00 - 11:30	Coffee break
11:30 - 12:30	Agenda-setting for the working groups sessions Here, we will discuss the working group process and open up the agenda for working group proposals.
12:30 - 14:00	Lunch break
14:00 - 15:30	Working group parallel discussions
15:30 - 16:00	Coffee break
16:00 - 17:00	OPTIONAL - Working group parallel discussions, continued OPTIONAL - Kanchanaburi train
17:00 onwards	Free time. Dinner on your own.
<p>Day 4 (24 July / Thursday) Location: Monthathip @ Dheva Mantra Hotel in Kanchanaburi</p>	

09:00 - 10:00	Opening the day and agenda setting
10:00 - 11:30	<p>Parallel Session Block 1 (90 mins)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Membership and Partnerships Committee: <i>Affirming our Network Membership Structure</i> • Research and Comms Committee: <i>CSID Network Comms Strategy</i> • Governance Committee: <i>Committee Term Limits and (S)election process</i> • Ad Hoc Working Group Committee: <i>Clarifying the Working Group Selection and Funding Process</i> • <i>Emergent Network Sessions (as proposed)</i> <p>Coffee Break: 10:45 - 11:15</p>
11:30 - 12:30	Lunch
12:30 - 12:45	Return to Monathip Meeting Room prepared to start the next session on time at 12:45pm.
12:45 - 14:15	<p>Parallel Session Block 2 (90 mins)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance Committee: <i>Reporting & Information Sharing Practices</i> • Fellows: <i>Building Local Communities of Practice</i> • Membership and Partnerships Committee: <i>Affirming our Onboarding and Outreach Activities</i> • Fundraising & Finance Committee: <i>Inclusive Participation Fund</i> • <i>Emergent Network Sessions (as proposed)</i>
14:15 - 15:00	<p>Coffee break (15 minutes)</p> <p>Gallery walk (30 minutes)</p>
15:00 - 16:00	<p>What comes next? From Recommendation to Reality - Synchronous Session with Virtual Gathering</p> <p>Closing the day</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Space tomorrow morning to self-organize continued conversation, if desired
16:00 - 17:00	All Hands Committee Meeting (Current Committee Members Only)

Day 5 (25 July / Friday)

Location: Monthathip @ Dheva Mantra Hotel in Kanchanaburi

09:00 - 12:00	<p>Networking time and closing the 2025 CSIDNet Thailand Gathering</p> <p>Until 11 AM - Networking Time <i>This could be time for you to organise conversations or follow-up meetings that you didn't have time for during the last few days. If you want to invite other people into your conversations / meeting, please send a message to the Whatsapp Group.</i></p> <p>11 AM - Back to main room for us to close the 2025 CSIDNet Thailand Gathering</p>
12:00 - 13:30	Lunch and checking out of the hotel
13:30 - 16:00	<p>OPTIONAL - opt-in for visit to Mahidol Bremen Medical Informatics Research Unit (MIRU), Faculty of ICT, Mahidol University en route back to Eastin Hotel (2 vans)</p> <p>There's a sign-up sheet for those interested to join the visit.</p>
13:30 - 16:00	Travel back to Eastin Hotel, Bangkok (4 vans)
13:30 - 16:00	Travel directly to BKK Airport, Bangkok (1 van)
Onwards	Dinner on your own in Bangkok

Day 6 (26 July / Saturday)

- Check out of Eastin Phayathai
- International participants departure

Appendix 2: Details of the Day 1 Parallel Thematic Sessions

- Advances in Multi-Scale and Predictive Modeling for Climate-Sensitive Disease Forecasting – Leonardo Rafael Lopez, Sisay Adall
- Citizen Science and Participatory Approaches – Karen Cheruto Bett
 - This session facilitated a discussion on the place of citizen science data in infectious disease modelling. We shared findings from our ongoing study and co-created some ideas to take forward.
- Principles and Ethics of Generative AI in CSID Tools - Shakira Babirye
 - This session introduced fundamental principles of generative AI and its ethical implications in the development and deployment of CSID tools, including bias, data privacy, and accountability. It explored the balance between AI automation and human decision-making in disease response, and how AI-generated insights can support disease surveillance, forecasting, and intervention strategies while ensuring responsible and transparent use.
- Antimicrobial Resistance and Environmental Drivers – Muhammad Asaduzzaman
 - Our planet is rushing towards a post-antibiotic era and the global burden of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is rising. The session showed the plausible transmission of clinically significant resistant organisms to human beings from the environment including fresh water, waste water, soil, air, and wildlife. We discussed the spatiotemporal distribution, risk factors, climate impacts, and potential recommendations for AMR mitigation, particularly in LMIC settings.
- Storms, Natural Disasters, and Infectious Diseases - Kelly Searle
 - Climate change is increasing natural disasters globally, with both direct and indirect impacts on infectious disease transmission and risk. Measuring these impacts poses challenges for logistics and response. This session explored those challenges, and discussed possible approaches. We also discussed how our projects can collaborate with response organizations for data collection and integration of our tools.
- Vector-Borne Infectious Diseases and the Role of Climate Change – Ibrahima Diouf, Daniel Villela, Jared Norman
- Feasibility and Appropriateness of Ensemble Models in LMICs – Angkana Huang
 - Ensemble modeling hubs provide a coherent interface for policymakers and the public to interface with modeling outputs, and have substantially facilitated the communications between modeling groups leading to cross-learning and better modeling practices. However, the redundancy of efforts poses the question of whether it is suitable for LMICs where resources are already terribly strained. This session discussed the design of data inputs and outputs that would enable models built for a particular context to run across multiple LMIC settings, such that groups

working on multiple places combined could feasibly run ensemble hubs in LMICs and cross-learn despite resource constraints.

- Co-Designing a Simulation Game for CSID - Sebastian Bernal-Garcia
 - This session focused on co-designing a simulation game that enhances understanding and adoption of CSID models. The discussion revolved around game rule and mechanics, user interface and experience, and model attributes. Participants engaged with an early-stage version of a simulation game developed in Stella. By gathering feedback from diverse experts, this session aimed to create a more relevant, user-friendly, and scientifically sound simulation tool for climate-driven mosquito-borne diseases.
- Risk Communication for Climate-Sensitive Infectious Diseases - Sharon Tshipa
 - This session explored communication strategies for CSID risks. As climate change continues to influence the spread and severity of infectious diseases, timely and accurate risk communication is essential for public awareness, policy action, and community preparedness. This roundtable helped identify communication gaps, share best practices, and develop recommendations for improving risk communication strategies. By strengthening communication approaches, the CSIDNet community can enhance its impact in raising awareness and promoting evidence-based responses to climate-driven health risks.
- Open Science, R Packages, and Research Software Development – Yanina Bellini Saibene, Samuel Schildhauer
 - <https://ropensci.org/blog/2025/08/26/csidnet-agm-2025/>

Flash Talks: Showcase of Early Warning Systems and Tools

 Flash Talk Slides: CSIDNet.pptx